

THE CONCEPT OF HAZARD LEVELS OF SUBSTANCES

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There are the following common procedures for classifying the degree of danger of substances:

The hazard class according to the National classifier is a conditional magnitude of harmful effects and is determined for various objects – chemicals in proportion to network regulatory documents.

Hazard class of harmful substances – a conditional magnitude designed for simplified classification of potentially hazardous substances by the degree of their effect on the body, harmful substances are divided into four hazard classes:

Grade 1. Extremely dangerous substances;

Grade 2. Substances with high risk;

Grade 3. Moderately dangerous substances;

Grade 4. Substances with low risk;

The hazard class of harmful substances depends on norms and indicators. Indicators according to **GOST 12.1.007-76** should correspond to the following norms (see Table 1).

Table 1

Hazard class standards by national standard

Indicator	Hazard class norms			
	I	II	III	IV
Permissible concentration of harmful substances in the working zone – Reg (PDK), mg / m ³	<0,1	0,1-1,0	1,1-10,0	>10,0
Average death dose (LD50), when administered in the stomach, 1 kg / mg	<15	15-150	151-5000	>5000
Average death dose (LD50), when applied to the skin, 1 kg / mg	<100	100-500	501-2500	>2500
Average death dose (LD50), in air, mg / m ³	<500	500-5000	5001-50000	>50 000
Coefficient of probability of	>300	300-30	29-3	<3

absorption				
Acute impact zone	<6,0	6,0-18,0	18,1-54,0	>54,0
Zone of chronic influence	>10,0	10,0-5,0	4,9-2,5	<2,5

Experimental method. For the experimental determination of toxicological properties of substances, it is necessary to evaluate the hazard class and other similar indicators. In order to achieve a high degree of Accuracy, It is recommended to carry out research on Toxicity Testing in two to three types of animals or in test cultures (strains, etc.).k.) the transfer will be appropriate.

Calculation method. Together with a complete analytical study of the object, the toxicological properties of individual substances are also based on the database. Since Toxicological Research on an object requires high costs, in practice the calculation method is used consciously bypassing a number of delimitations [7, 8].

Hazard class by international standards.

NFPA 704-National Fire Protection Association (National Fire Protection Association) is a commercial and industrial association with the participation of America and some countries that provides fire, electricity and construction security. Its headquarters are located in the city of Queens, Massachusetts. It was founded in 1896. Its main mission is to conduct research, training and introduce standards, codes to reduce the likelihood of the occurrence of fires and other natural-man-made disasters around the world.

Currently, the "fire diamond" for any brand is the "fire diamond", that is, the field of The Shape of an equilateral Rhombus, which provides the possibility of equipment, equipment, procedures and precautions that must be applied by the personnel of emergency services in emergency events related to hazardous materials as part of immediate first aid, is divided into 4 equal pieces painted

Figure 1. Fire diamond-containers marked with " fire diamond – and safety indicator:

In this case, blue is marked for health risks, red – for fire hazards, yellow – for chemical stability, and white-for special codes for various hazards. The first three categories are evaluated on a scale from 0 (stable substance, safe) to 4 (dangerous to the point of Death) (see Table 2).

Table 2

Hazard class standards by international standards

Dangerous to health (Blue color)	
4	When exposed to too little time, it leads to death or major damage with complications (e.g. thianid acid, tetraethylquin, phosphine)
3	Severe temporary, with a short period of exposure, can lead to a complication consequence of medium duration (for example, potassium hydroxide, chlorine, sulfuric acid)
2	There is a possibility of temporary loss of working capacity or other complication damage as a result of non-chronic intensive or continuous exposure (for example, ethanol, diethyl ether, chloroform)
1	Has a minimal complication injury-causing effect (e.g. benzophenone, acetone)
0	Safe for health, no precautions required (maslan, lanolin, baking soda)
Flame retardant (red)	
4	At the usual atmospheric pressure and temperature, it evaporates completely or spreads easily into the air and takes fire (for example, pentans, acetylene, propane) with a flash temperature of 23 °C (73 °F)
3	Flammable liquids and solids at ambient temperature. The Flash temperature is in the range of 23 °C (73 °F) and 38 °C (100 °F). (for example, butanal-1, benzal, acetone)
2	It ignites as a result of some heating or relatively high air temperatures (naprimer, phenol, diesel fuel). The Flash temperature is between 38 °C (100 °F) and 93 °C (200 °F)
1	It must be heated to ignite m (for example, soy oil). Flash Temperature 93 °C (200 °F)
0	Non-flammable substance (e.g. water)
Instability/reactivity (yellow)	
4	At normal pressure and temperature, it undergoes detonation or can explode and decompose (for example, nitroglycerin, ternary-butylium, hexogen)
3	As a result of external influence, when heated in a closed place, it undergoes detonation or can explode and decompose, exploding with water or detonating when hit strongly. (for example, potassium perchlorate, ammonium nitrate)

2	Undergoes serious chemical changes at high temperature and pressure, reacts violently with water or forms an explosive mixture (for example, phosphorus, potassium, sodium)
1	It is usually stable, but can become unstable at high temperatures and pressures (such as hydrogen peroxide, sodium bicarbonate)
0	It is stable to the effects of open flames and is not exposed to water (such as argon, helium)

White color-special.

White is the area of special characters – and can be marked with different symbols:

W: reacts with water in an unusual or dangerous way (for example, cesium, sodium, rubidium)

OX ili OXY: oxidizer (e.g. potassium perchlorate, ammonium nitrate)

SA: suffocating gas (does not help breathing, is not toxic) (nitrogen, helium, neon, argon, krypton, xenon)

Non-standard characters.

Note: these symbols are not part of the **NFPA 704** standard, but are sometimes used informally. Informal symbols may be required, allowed, or banned by the competent authorities (e.g. firefighters).

COR: corrosive (visual. Corrosive); strong acid or alkali (e.g. sulfuric acid, potassium hydroxide)

ACID (visual aid) Acid-acid) **I ALK** (visual. Alkali-alkali)

☠/ **BIO:** biological risk (e.g. smallpox virus)

☠ / **POI/tax:** (visual. Poison): zakharli (for example, Bee Zakhar, tetraethylcarthy, barium chloride, thallium sulfate, potassium tsianide, cadmium acetate, nicotine)

(radiation spark) or **RA/RAD:** radioactive (e.g. plutoni, uranium, polonium hydride, potassium diuranate)

CRY or CRYO (visually. Cryogenic): lower temperature (e.g. liquid nitrogen).

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